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Research Article

RESPONSE ON THE WAY TO FIRST-LINE ANTIRETROVIRAL THERAPY WITHIN HIV PATIENTS

¹Dr. Zainub Jaleel, ²Dr. Momna Jaleel, ²Dr. Rafia Kamran

¹House Officer, PIMS, Islamabad

²House Officer Jinnah Hospital Lahore

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Abstract:

Objective: This study was focused to evaluate the immune recovery amongst patients infected with HIV on the antiretroviral therapy by a one-year follow-up.

Methodology: This study was patients' retrospective analysis on Antiretroviral therapy discussed by different Voluntary Testing and Counselling centres. The study held at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from October 2017 to November 2018. The patients above 18 years of age, with CD4 count less than 350 cells/mm³ and who were WHO clinical stage III /IV were considered eligible for ART and were enrolled in the study.

Results: A number of 800 patients comprising over 73.45% were males and they had no travel history (60%). The majority of patients (58.90%) were having stage IV and 23.65% followed by stage III. More than half the strength of patients (411/800) had described heterosexual contact for a risk factor for infection of HIV. A significant increase was observed within the CD4 cell count at the follow-up in comparison with baseline (183.30 ± 24.60 Vs. 308.80 ± 36.25). In the same way, the viral load amongst the patients on Antiretroviral therapy significantly decreases as a result of therapy at six months.

Conclusion: In the end, it was concluded that in the consequences of Antiretroviral therapy CD4 cell count rises and viral load declines significantly. So, long term combined Antiretroviral therapy can possibly restore and improve the immune status within HIV infected patients.

Keywords: Antiretroviral Therapy, ART, CD4, HIV, Viral Load.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Zainub Jaleel,

House Officer, PIMS, Islamabad

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The antiretroviral therapy facility is an indispensable element of HIV epidemic response within underdeveloped countries. At present, with the growing number of patients receiving ART, a decrease has been documented in AIDS-related mortality [1]. In Pakistan, the HIV epidemic has grown from a low occurrence to an intense epidemic. The occurrence of HIV within the country was stated less than one percent, with an approximation 0.1 Million cases [2]. In the last few years, Pakistanis deported from Gulf countries were reported as a single largest HIV infected group with the lowest prevalence amongst high-risk groups [3]. However current surveillance data from Pakistan showed that the rate of infection is rising among users of injecting drugs, transsexual/transvestite sex workers and males having sex with males [2]. Antiretroviral therapy efforts to stop viral replication. There is availability for many different antiretroviral drug classes like as Non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors, Nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors, and protein inhibitors. Antiretroviral first-line regimen comprises lamivudine, zidovudine (AZT), stavudine (d4T), efavirenz (EFV) and nevirapine (NVP) while tenofovir, ritonavir /lopinavir, and didanosine are introduced as second-line regimen [2]. These regimens have changed HIV into a chronic disease in spite of fatal disease with lifelong destruction of the replication of HIV [4]. A very few types of research studied have examined immune recovery as a consequence of ART usage. Maximum of these research studies reporting clinical, immunological and virologic response to ART amongst patients infected with HIV were from prosperous countries where ART was started at relatively higher CD4 count. The Data on the recovery of immune amongst HIV infected patients within Pakistan is not sufficient. our study was directed to describe HIV patients initiated on ART within clinics of Punjab. Furthermore, determining the immune recovery amongst HIV patients on Antiretroviral therapy was also focused in this study.

METHODS:

This study was patients' retrospective analysis on Antiretroviral therapy discussed by different Voluntary Testing and Counselling centres. The study held at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from October 2017 to November 2018. The patients infected with HIV were referred by different Voluntary testing and Counselling (VTC), centres situated at various districts within Punjab province. The hospital facilitated roundabout (1500) patients with (873) were

on ART. In our study the enrolled patients were above 18 years of age they visited the Facility and were placed on ART therapy within the study period. Patients with CD4 count <350 cells/mm³ or the patients who were WHO clinical stage III /IV were considered suitable for ART and were included in the study. Patients having concurrent infections and serious illness were excluded and they received ART with respect to national guidelines [5]. One NNRTI and Two NRTI regimen were utilized as first-line therapy. Two regimens were utilized; Lamivudine + Zidovudine as a Nevirapine (Efavirenz in patients on antitubercular treatment) and Stavudine + lamivudine and NRTI as an NRTI and Nevirapine (Efavirenz within patient on anti-tubercular treatment). The value of Hemoglobin of 8 gm/dl was considered as cut off for anaemia. The anaemic patients were positioned regimen which was based on stavudine. A questionnaire was designed according to recorded data. The demographic information including education, gender, age, occupation, risk factors for HIV, travel history, the treatment regimen for ART and WHO clinical staging of HIV disease was collected. The Baseline data of haemoglobin and CD4 lymphocyte counts at the time of ART initialization were recovered from records of patients. CD4 count at one-year follow-up was noted and Patients were also followed for one year. Informed consent was obtained from all the participant patients before their enrollment within the study. Confidentiality and Anonymity of the patient's records and data were maintained during the research. Necessary ethical approvals were obtained by the ethical review committee of the hospital. IBM SPSS Statistics was utilized for data entry and analysis. statistics were descriptively performed. Categorical variables were summarized using percentage and frequency and quantitative variables were presented through mean (SD). The result of interest was enhanced within the CD4 cell count. paired t-test was used for comparing CD4 cell count at baseline as well as at the end of follow-up (at 1 year). p-value < 0.05 was statistically significant.

RESULTS:

In our study retrospective analysis was presented. All participant patients were given informed consent and patients satisfying the inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. Out of 800 patients, 587 were males (73.40%) and round about sixty-one percent of patients were not having travel history. More than 60% of patients (512/800) were having lower education levels and round about 46% (369/800) were professional degree holders. Roundabout fifty-one percent of patients (410/800) described heterosexual associates as a risk factor for the

infection of HIV. Maximum of the strength around 58.86% of patients were with stage IV, followed by stage III around 23.63%. Roundabout 110 patients (13.75%) were not in contact for follow-up. Therefore, Antiretroviral therapy was done upon a total of 626 patients (78.25%) at the end of the research study period (one-year follow-up). The comparison of viral load and CD4 lymphocyte cell count was made at the initial stage and within six months follow-up. A

significant difference was observed within both calculations. A significant increase was observed in CD4 cell count as in comparison to the initial stage (184.28 ± 24.57 Vs. 308.80 ± 36.24 ; p-value). Furthermore, on Antiretroviral therapy, the viral load amongst patients was significantly reduced as a consequence of therapy at the time of six months. p-value = 0.001.

Table – I: Baseline Features

Baseline Characteristics		Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	587	73.4
	Female	213	26.6
Travel History	Travelled out of Pakistan	257	32.13
	No travel history for self but spouse travelled	69	8.63
	No travel history for self or spouse	474	59.24
Occupation	Skilled	170	21.25
	Unskilled	182	22.73
	Professionals	199	24.88
	Housewives	123	15.38
	Transgender sex workers	17	2.13
	Others (including unknown)	109	13.63
Education	Illiterate	288	36
	Primary	141	17.63
	Secondary	228	28.5
	College	143	17.87
Risk factor for HIV exposure	Heterosexual Contact	410	51.25
	Male homosexual/ bisexual contact	110	13.75
	Injecting drug use	195	24.38
	Blood products	41	5.13
	Unknown	44	4.49
WHO clinical staging of HIV disease at presentation	Stage I	83	10.38
	Stage II	57	7.13
	Stage III	189	23.63
	Stage IV	471	58.86

Table – II: One Year Follow-Up Status

One Year Follow-Up	Percentage
Expired	8
Loss to Follow-up	14
On Therapy	78

Table – III: Comparison of Viral Load and CD4

CD4 and Viral Load	Baseline	Six Month Follow-up	P-Value
CD4 (cell/mm ³)	183.27 ± 24.56	308.79 ± 36.23	0.001
Viral load	2.98 x 10 ⁴ ± 138.76	1.54 x 10 ⁴ ± 127.63	

DISCUSSION:

At the end of the study, the conclusions represented a significant rise within CD4 cell count and a large decrease within viral load among patients of HIV on antiretroviral therapy. The average CD4 T-cell count after the duration of six months the follow-up was higher significantly as in comparison with the starting point. Furthermore, the mean viral load at the time of follow-up was significantly inferior as compared to its baseline evaluation. Previous studies have shown the same results as indicated in this study. The antiretroviral therapy has shown an improved effect within disease progression laboratory markers [6]. Early starting of the ART therapy is prone to be helpful to reduce the acute disease severity, reduction of viral mutation rate and for altering the earlier viral set point. It is important to note that viral replication suppression will improve the functioning of immune as well as decrease the transmission of viral risk throughout the higher infectivity HIV stage [6]. Viral suppression aimed at the prolonged period is observed associated with CD4 T-lymphocyte count and reduction in the rate of opportunistic infection which further decreases both mortality and morbidity [6]. In comparison with the previous studies, the average CD4 cell count at follow-up was found slightly lower in this study [7, 8]. A study directed within Western Ethiopia stated that CD4 T lymphocytes displayed significant upgrading at a duration of two years follow-up amongst patients of HIV on mutual antiretroviral therapy [9]. The usage of antiretroviral therapy for the duration of 2 to 4 years have indicated the mean counting of CD4 cell increased round about within the range of 200 to 300 cell/ μ l, along with the CD4 rate increase falling over time [10, 11]. A study in Tanzania stated that, amongst 171 participant patients, more than ninety percent were having increment within their CD4 cell count along with an average rise of more than 150 cell/ μ l as in comparison with baseline [12]. A study held in Pakistan also stated many comparable findings [13]. The study emphasized on significant upgrading within both CD4 cell count and viral load was seen at follow-up when patients of HIV were kept on combining antiretroviral therapy. The pre-treatment mean viral load was 3.22 x (10 raise to power 4) and the follow-up was 1.61 x (10 raise to power 4). In the same way, the mean CD4 cell count at the starting point and

follow-up also indicated significant upgrading with an average rise of 200 cell/ μ l. A number of factors have influenced the immune response as described within literature. The starting point CD4 cell count is linked with immunological results. Patients possessing lower baseline CD4 cell count starting mutual antiretroviral therapy have indicated weak immune response at the time of follow-up [14]. Furthermore, young patients have shown better immunological results as in comparison with elders [14]. In our study, the average age of the study participant was 32 years. The HIV patients in our study denoted a younger age group as the mean age of the participant patients was 32, with a reduction of advancing age thymic functions. So, an improved immune response can be explained for this younger population. Our study design was retrospectively having its own limitations as incomplete documentation, non-uniformity and missing values within the time interval among cell count of CD4 T cell lymphocytes and viral load. Furthermore, the follow-up period in our research study was round about six months where viral load and CD4 cell count were determined. Multiple and longer follow-up periods along with calculations is found more revealing. In generating useful information related to Antiretroviral therapy within the province of Punjab. The outcomes of the existing study will be beneficial within identifying factors related to CD4 T cell lymphocytes recovery and generating hypothesis for future prospective studies for evaluating immune response amongst HIV patients started on Antiretroviral therapy.

CONCLUSION:

In the end, it was concluded that in the consequences of Antiretroviral therapy CD4 cell count rises and viral load declines significantly. So, long term combined Antiretroviral therapy can possibly restore and improve the immune status within HIV infected patients.

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